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Mechanical realization and low power RF test of the two RF guns

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ABSTRACT

Work Package 7.4 aimed to design, construct, and test two very high cathode peak field C-band (5.712 GHz) electron photo-guns. The two devices, one Standing Wave (SW) and one Travelling Wave (TW) have been designed and realized. The SW gun has been designed by INFN and fabricated by COMEB while the TW gun has been designed by PSI, machined by VDL and finally brazed by PSI. In this Deliverable we report the details on the mechanical realization of the two guns and on low power RF test results in terms of scattering coefficients, coupling coefficient and electric field measurements.

I.FAST Consortium, 2024

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Executive summary

In this Deliverable Report, we summarize the activities related to the mechanical realization process and low power radiofrequency (rf) test of the two photo-guns that have been developed in the framework of the Task 7.4. Both devices operate in the C-band (5.712 GHz) regime, one is a Standing Wave (SW) and the other is a Traveling Wave (TW) device. The SW gun is a 2.5 cell cavity with a four-port mode launcher, designed to operate with short rf pulses (300 ns) and cathode peak field larger than 160 MV/m. The gun cells are made up of Oxygen Free High Conductivity (OFHC) copper and has been realized with the new technology without brazing, developed at INFN, that allows to assemble the gun cells with special gaskets and to proceed, after the vacuum test, directly to the rf characterization and test. A particular effort has been put on the design of the cooling system that allows to operate the gun at repetition frequencies larger than 400 Hz. The rf measurements have been done after the assembly and vacuum test of the gun. They clearly show a very good agreement with simulations both in term of quality factor, resonant frequency and electric field profile, as illustrated in the document.

The TW gun is a unique 11.5-cell gun fed by an on-axis coaxial waveguides and designed to operate with RF pulse lengths of 100 ns and a peak electric field of 200 MV/m. The gun cells are similar made from Oxygen Free High Conductivity (OFHC) copper and brazed together using the PSI tuning-free technology. The low attenuation of the RF power and short filling time means that the TW photogun opens up the possibility of very high repetition rate operation. After the successful machining of the cells and brazing of the structure, the low power measurements were performed demonstrating a high level of agreement with the simulations. This is demonstrated through a reflection coefficient of less than -30 dB, a field flatness of 1.66% and a mean phase advance per cell of 120.03 degrees.

1 Introduction

Rf photo-guns are widely used in modern particle accelerator facilities, particularly in FELs, as they provide very low-emittance, high-brightness electron bunches. They are key in such accelerator facilities and, presently, primarily operated in the S band regime (3 GHz) achieving cathode peak fields of 80-120 MV/m and repetition rates lower than 120 Hz. Task 7.4 has been focused to the design, fabrication, and test of two new rf photo-guns operating in the C-band (5.712 GHz) frequency. In an RF photo-gun the cathode is embedded in the rf structure. An external rf power source (typically klystron) excites the cavity's accelerating mode so that, with the introduction of a laser pulse on the cathode at a short enough wavelength, photo-electrons are emitted and immediately accelerated through high electric fields. Under the combined action of the rf accelerating field and of an external solenoidal magnetic field, the dynamics of the electron beam are guided and controlled, and low-emittance, high-brightness bunches are produced and injected in the accelerating structures placed downstream. The achievable beam brightness in rf photo-injectors is strongly dependent on the cathode peak field [1]. For this reason, in the last generation rf guns, a great effort has been put to increase the field amplitude keeping under control the breakdown rate probability (BDR) [2]. In this context, the possibility to implement a new C band photo-gun capable to reach cathode peak field larger than 150 MV/m, is strongly attractive for both the reachable beam parameters [3,4] and compactness than for the possibility to operate at high repetition rate (up to 1 kHz) using short RF

pulses, as proposed for the X-band linacs of the EuPRAXIA@SPARCLAB project [5] and XLS design study [6]. The guns are also extremely attractive for its possible applications in upgrades of existing photo-injectors for FEL [4] and compact facilities for industrial and medical applications [7]. The C-band frequency regime (5.712 GHz) is a more recent technology whose reliability and effectiveness have been already fully demonstrated. The technology is also industrially mature, since power sources and the needed ancillary components (driver amplifiers, waveguides, ceramic windows, dummy loads, LLRFs, isolators and pulse compressors) are all available on the market. However, beam injectors fully based on this technology are yet to be developed.

In the framework of the Task 7.4, two different photo-guns have been designed, realized and tested: a SW over-coupled cavity made of two-and-a-half cells and a multi-cell TW accelerating section incorporating a photocathode in the very first cell. Both approaches are attractive, with different advantages that have been investigated in term of beam dynamics performances [3,4].

The SW gun has been realized without brazing, with the new technology developed at INFN [8] and already adopted for the realization of RF photoguns in S band [9-11]. The technology allows to assemble the device using special gaskets in a clean room and to proceed, after the vacuum test, directly to the rf characterization and test. The main advantage is the possibility to use forged, not annealed, copper that, according to X-band high gradient tests [12] and tests on S band guns [9-11] has been verified to exhibit extremely good performances in term of conditioning time and BDR.

The TW gun has been realised with tuning-free brazing, a technology developed within PSI and used for the realization of the SwissFEL C-band linear accelerator. The technology has demonstrated extremely good high gradient performance at the S-,C- and X-band frequencies bands.

The two guns have been designed and fabricated in a strong collaborations between public research institutions and private companies. In particular the SW gun has been designed by INFN and fabricated by COMEB while the TW gun has been designed by PSI, machined by VDL and finally brazed by PSI. The beam dynamics studies have been performed in collaboration by INFN and PSI [3,4].

The present report illustrates the realization process and the low power rf test performed on the fabricated guns.

2 Standing Wave Gun realization and test

The SW photo-gun is a 2.5 cell structure, and its design has been optimized to minimize the peak E field, the modified Poynting vector [13], the rf pulse length and pulsed heating [14]. For this reason the gun has been designed with a coupling coefficient equal to 3 to allow operation with short rf pulses (300 ns) thus reducing the BDR, pulsed heating and the power dissipation. An elliptical profile of the iris with large aperture has been also implemented to reduce the peak electric field, to increase the frequency separation with the nearest $\pi/2$ -mode thus avoiding excitation of this mode with short rf pulses and to have a better pumping on the cathode cell. A four-port mode launcher [15, 16] with an on-axis coupling has been also adopted to reduce the pulsed heating on the coupler and to have a perfect compensation of the dipole and quadrupole field components. The mode launcher has been also designed to integrate two pumping ports. The main rf parameters are reported in Table 1. Other details on the electromagnetic and thermo-mechanical can be found in the Milestone MS28 and in published papers [15, 16].

The 3D mechanical layout of the whole SW injector is given in Fig. 1. The gun is followed by an emittance compensating solenoid and a laser injection chamber that allows the laser injection with the last mirror in air.

Table 1: Main Parameters of the C-band Gun (in parenthesis the measured ones)

Parameter	Value
Resonant frequency	5.712 (5.712)
$E_{\text{cath}}/\sqrt{P_{\text{diss}}}$ [MV/(m·MW ^{0.5})]	51.4
rf input power [MW]	18(19)
Cathode peak field [MV/m]	160
Rep. rate [Hz]	100-400
Quality factor	11900 (11900)
Filling time [ns]	166 (147)
Coupling coefficient	3 (3.5)
rf pulse length [ns]	300
Mode sep. π - $\pi/2$ [MHz]	47 (48.3)
$E_{\text{surf}}/E_{\text{cath}}$	0.96
Mod. Poy. vector [W/ μm^2]	2.5
Pulsed heating [°C]	16
Average diss. Power [W]	250-1000

Figure 1: Mechanical drawing of the full gun assembly.

2.1 MECHANICAL REALIZATION OF THE SW GUN

The gun integrates several different components: the standing wave (SW) cells, the four-port mode launcher and the cathode. The mode launcher has been machined using the five-axis milling machine Micron UCP600 Vario with precision on the internal dimensions of $\pm 8 \mu\text{m}$ and roughness below 200 nm. It has then been brazed in a vacuum furnace using palcusil 5 alloy. Pictures of the machined mode launcher before and after brazing are given in Fig. 2. After brazing it has been vacuum tested.

The SW cells and cathode have been machined using, for the final finishing of the surfaces the lathe Schaublin 225 TM-CNC. Pictures of the machined cells before the final assembly are reported in Fig. 3. The internal dimensions of the cells have been machined with a precision of $\pm 2 \mu\text{m}$ to avoid tuning and a surface roughness below 30 nm. After the machining, the cells have been cleaned using a bath of Almeco, followed by an NGL cleaning at 50 °C and a final treatment in citric acid at 40 deg to remove the oxidations. They have been finally washed with demineralized water in an ultrasonic bath and dried with pure nitrogen. After the cleaning the cells have been also heated in a vacuum furnace at 200 °C for 2 hours to remove the residual water from the surfaces.

Figure 2: Pictures of The Machined Mode Launcher Before (a) and After Brazing (b).

Figure 3: Pictures of The SW Copper Cells and gaskets.

The gun has been finally assembled. As already pointed out, the gun accelerating cells have been assembled without brazing, with the new technology developed at INFN. The mounting procedure of the cells on the gun is reported in Fig. 4. In all the mounting procedure the gun has been flushed with dry nitrogen. The mounting procedure foresaw the use of two special gaskets. The external one, in aluminum for vacuum seal and the internal one with a special copper gasket for the rf contact. The alignment of the cells has been guaranteed, during the mounting procedure, using two special “V” precise tools has shown in Fig. 4(c).

The gun, after the final assembly, has been vacuum tested with leak rate sensitivity below 1×10^{-11} mbar/l/s. The picture of the final assembled gun under vacuum tests is given in Fig. 4(d). The assembled gun has been mechanically characterized, after the final assembly, using a CMM ALTERA 10.7.7 (Fig. 5b) and the alignment of the cells has been verified to be, in both planes, below ± 40 μm .

Figure 4: Pictures of The Gun Under Assembly: (A) Assembly of The Cells; (B) Cathode Insertion; (C) Cell Alignment Before the Final Clamping; (D) Vacuum Test.

Figure 5: (a) RF Tests of The Gun; (b) Mechanical Characterization of the Gun With CMC.

Also the vacuum chambers (for laser injection and pumping) and the gun support have been realized. The emittance compensation solenoid has been designed and fabricated. This last device is a single coil device with a length of 12 cm and a bore radius of 30 mm, whose main parameters are reported in Table 2.

The gun, after the final assembly and vacuum test, has been assembled in its final configuration with the solenoid and vacuum chambers as displayed in Fig. 6.

Table 2: Main Parameters of the C-band Gun solenoid.

Parameter	Value
B_{\max} (T)	0.79
Bore radius (mm)	30
Solenoid length (mm)	126
Yoke material	Low Carbon Steel
Integrated field (T mm)	64.5
Good field region radius (mm)	10 mm
Integrated field variation	3×10^{-5}
Number of turns	280
Conductor dimension (mm)	$6 \times 6 = \text{bore } 4$
Nominal current (A)	184
Nominal voltage (V)	6
Inductance (mH)	3
Resistance (m Ω)	178
Water flow rate (l/min)	4.5
Temperature drop ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	18
Pressure drop (bar)	3

Figure 6: Picture of the assembled gun with solenoid, vacuum system, support and vacuum chambers.

2.2 LOW POWER RF TEST RESULTS OF THE SW GUN

The assembled gun has been rf tested using a Network Analyzer R&S ZVB 20 (Fig. 5(a)). The measurements have been done under nitrogen flux. The reflection coefficient at the input port is reported in Fig. 7. The three modes are clearly visible in the plot. The frequency of operation, quality factor and coupling coefficient obtained by fitting the reflection coefficient are reported in Table 1 and compared with simulations. They clearly show that the frequency and quality factor of the working mode are the nominal ones while the coupling coefficient is slightly larger. The reasons of this discrepancy are still under investigation and are probably related to the different dimensions of the first coupling iris. This value of the coupling coefficient does not affect significantly the gun performances in term of required power, rf pulse length and cathode peak field. The electric field on axis has been measured using a metallic bead of 2 mm diameter connected to a nylon wire, dropping into the gun. The result of this measurement is reported in Fig. 8. The field unbalance between the cells is at the level of 5%. With the bead drop technique it is not possible to measure the cathode peak field at the cathode plane because of the effects of image currents that affect the measurement itself. The field at the cathode position, extrapolated by a local fit of the measurements, has a value comparable with the field on the first cell, 5% below the central one. The reason of this discrepancy with respect to the ideal simulated value are probably due to the small deformation of the special copper gaskets used to guarantee the rf contact and tolerances in the fabrication that, even if at the level of few μm , can still affect the field flatness.

Figure 7: Reflection Coefficient at The Gun Input Port.

Figure 8: Electric Field Profile on Axis Measured by Bead Drop Technique.

3 Travelling Wave Gun realization and test

The TW photo-gun is an 11.5 cell structure operating at the $2\pi/3$ mode. The design aims to achieve the have the greatest electric field strength on the cathode while keeping the pulsed surface heating to below 50 K [14]. This ensures that the peak electric field within the structure, that will ultimately limit the operational gradient, are used for the generation of the electrons. To reduce the effects of pulse surface heating, the design uses very short RF pulses facilitated by the TW nature of the device. A comprehensive description of the RF and mechanical design were given in the MS28 report and published in [8]. Below details the mechanical realization of the device and the low power testing.

3.1 MECHANICAL REALIZATION OF THE TW GUN

The TW photo-gun was realised under the collaboration between VDL and PSI where the ultra-high precision machining from VDL is used in combination with PSI's stacking and brazing methodology to produce a tuning-free RF device. The machining of the cells and couplers were realised at VDL using ultra-high precision (UP) turning and milling. The machining process for the TW gun is detailed in left to right in Figure 9. Pre-machining defined the general shapes of the each of the components each of which were then moved for the turning for the cylindrically symmetric cells, and turning and milling for the more complex couplers. To conclude the machining the cells were machined with

VDL’s in-house developed devices. UP turning and milling that achieve an maximum deviation across the entire device of +/- 3 μm and and +/- 20 μm , respectively. The UP machined components were then packaged as demonstrated in Figure 10. The components were then shipped to PSI where they underwent stacking and brazing.

Figure 9: The machining steps carried out at VDL in the realization of the TW gun. Left to Right: Premachining, Pre-Milling, Fly-cutting, precision turning and ultra-precision milling.

Figure 10: The packaged TW gun components (left) and the packaged cathodes (right).

Stacking of the TW gun pieces was performed manually by PSI’s brazing expert. The first step of the stacking and brazing began with the coaxial couplers, including the waveguide and beampipe flanges. The brazing was performed with a copper-gold brazing wire with the melting temperature of the brazing wire reduced, through varying the copper-gold alloy ratio, for each brazing step. This brazing occurred over a total of three steps with the second step consisting of the completion of the input coupler’s coaxial and the third step being the regular cells with the full connection of the gun. Figure 11 demonstrates the stacking and brazing of the TW photogun at three different stages of the brazing process. After the final brazing step, the gun was mounted on its support structure as demonstrate in Figure 12.

Figure 11: The stacking and brazing of the travelling-wave rf photogun. Left: Brazed coaxial couplers of the gun. Middle: Manual stacking of the regular cells. Right: Stacked TW gun ready for the final brazing step.

Figure 12: Realised TW gun.

3.2 LOW POWER RF TEST RESULTS OF THE TW GUN

Low power measurements were performed at PSI in a recommissioned clean room in the building where the brazing took place. Given the load-lock capability of the gun, the low power measurements were the first instance of combining the TW photogun with the cathode manipulation system. The cathode was transversely aligned and inserted into the TW photogun using the manipulator's x-y-z translation capability. The S-parameters were measured using a R&S ZVA8 four-port network analyser, in the presence of flowing nitrogen and at the ambient temperature of the room of 25 degrees celsius. The nominal frequency of the photogun given these conditions was calculated by accounting for the nitrogen's permittivity, and the photogun's ambient and nominal operational temperature. The nominal z-position of the cathode was chosen to be the position at which the combined S11+S21 were below -30 dB. The S-parameters are displayed in Figure 14 where the TW nature of the device is observed through the lack of discrete modes rather a broad transmission of RF power. At the operational frequency of 5.712 GHz, the S11 and S22 are below -30 dB while the insert loss is 1.81 dB. The insertion loss is a little higher than the 1.41 dB expected. However, the waveguide transitions are not factored into the calibration and are expected to have an insertion loss of 0.1 - 0.2 dB, each.

With the cathode aligned, the bead was introduced into the system. For the work, we use a ceramic bead. The results of the bead-pull are illustrated in Figure 15. The top plot demonstrates the field amplitude with the cathode on the right at $z=4200$ and output coupler on the left. This was to prevent the impact of the initial accelerating of the bead distorting the field. The field flatness is observed to be very good with a peak variation of 1.66%. This validates the PSI technique of tuning-free designs. The phase advance per cell is observed to be very constant with a mean value over the structure with 120.03 degrees. Overall, the low power measurements demonstrate that the TW photogun was able to be realised with a high level of precision.

Figure 13: The low power testing of the TW gun.

Figure 14: The S-parameter measurements of the TW gun. Left: The reflection from the input coupler. Middle: The reflection from the output coupler. Right: The Insertion Loss through the photogun when power is fed from the input coupler.

Figure 15: Bead-pull measurements of the TW photogun. Top: The electric field amplitude plotted over the longitudinal (beam) axis. Bottom Left: The phase of the electric field plotted against the longitudinal position. Bottom Right: The imaginary and real components of the electric field.

4 Future plans and Conclusion

The SW and TW photo-guns have been fabricated and successfully low power tested. In the Deliverable we have reported all the details of the realization process and rf test. The SW gun has been now installed in the high power test stand at PSI and is under high power test. The results of these test will be illustrated in the final milestone M46. After the test of the SW gun we will proceed to the high power test of the TW gun and also these results will be the subject of the milestone MS46. The SW gun, after the conclusion of the high power test, will be installed in the Frascati TEX Facility [17] for beam production and experiments related to high brightness electron beam generation and

experiments. After the high power test of the TW gun, it will be also used for the test of field emission cathode in the framework of the I.FAST innovation Fund [7].

5 References

- [1] J.B. Rosenzweig and E. Colby, “Charge and Wavelength Scaling of RF Photoinjector Design”, Rep. TESLA-95-04, 1995.
- [2] V. A. Dolgashev, Y. Higashi, T. Higo, C. D. Nantista, and S. G. Tantawi, “RF Breakdown in Normal Conducting Single-cell Structures”, in Proc. PAC’05, Knoxville, TN, USA, May 2005, paper ROAC007, pp. 595–599.
- [3] A. Giribono et al., “Dynamics studies of high brightness electron beams in a normal conducting, high repetition rate C-band injector”, Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams, vol. 26, p. 083402, 2023.
- [4] T.G. Lucas et al., Toward a brightness upgrade to the SwissFEL: A high gradient traveling-wave rf photogun, Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams 26, 103401 (2023)
- [5] D. Alesini et al., “”EuPRAXIA@SPARC_LAB Conceptual Design Report”, INFN-18-03/LNF.
- [6] <http://www.compactlight.eu/Main/HomePage>
- [7] I.FAST Innovation Fund, PSI & VDL project, PI Prof. Dr. Mike Seidel
- [8] D. Alesini et al., International Patent Publication No. WO 2016/147118 A1, assigned to INFN.
- [9] D. Alesini et al., “New technology based on clamping for high gradient radio frequency photogun,”Phys. Rev. Spec. Top. Accel Beams, vol. 18, no. 9, Sep. 2015. doi:10.1103/physrevstab.18.092001
- [10] D. Alesini et al., “Design, realization, and high power test of high gradient, high repetition rate brazing-free S-band photogun,”Phys. Rev. Accel. Beams, vol. 21, no. 11, Nov. 2018. doi:10.1103/physrevaccelbeams.21.112001
- [11] V. Shpakov et al., “Design, optimization and experimental characterization of RF injectors for high brightness electron beams and plasma acceleration,”IEEE Open J. Instrum. Meas., vol. 17, no. 12, p. P12022, Dec. 2022. doi:10.1088/1748-0221/17/12/p12022
- [12] E. I. Simakov, V. A. Dolgashev, and S. G. Tantawi, “Advances in high gradient normal conducting accelerator structures,”Nucl. Instrum. Methods Phys. Res., Sect. A, vol. 907, pp. 221–230, Nov. 2018. doi:10.1016/j.nima.2018.02.085
- [13] A. Grudiev, S. Calatroni, and W. Wuensch, “New local field quantity describing the high gradient limit of accelerating structures,”Phys. Rev. Spec. Top. Accel Beams, vol. 12, no. 10, Oct. 2009. doi:10.1103/physrevstab.12.102001
- [14] V. A. Dolgashev, “High magnetic fields in couplers of X-band accelerating structures,”in PAC-03. IEEE, 2003. doi:10.1109/pac.2003.1289674.

- [15] D. Alesini et al., “The New C Band Gun for the Next Generation RF Photo-Injectors”, in Proc. IPAC’22, Bangkok, Thailand, Jun. 2022, pp. 679–682. doi:10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2022-MOPOMS021
- [16] D. Alesini et al., “Progress on the new high gradient C Band standing wave RF photo-gun”, in Proc. IPAC’23, Venice, Italy, May 2023, pp. 1374–1377. doi:10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2023-TUPA009
- [17] F. Cardelli et al. “Advancements in X-band technology at the TEX facility at INFN-LNF”, Proc. 15th International Particle Accelerator Conference, doi: 10.18429/JACoW-IPAC2024-TUPR02, JACoW Publishing, Geneva, Switzerland, 2024